

Welcome to CuttingGardens 2023!

You want to contribute to [CuttingGardens](#)? Run your own Garden! The material below is here to help you prepare.

First, here is the essential information you need to know about CuttingGardens:

1. What? CuttingGardens is a **distributed conference on cutting-edge methods for M/EEG data analysis**. It happens simultaneously in several locations (aka. Gardens) across the world, with a common global program, broadcasted to all locations simultaneously, and local programs made of talks, tutorials, posters, social events, satellites... as each Garden (optionally) sees fit. CuttingGardens is part of the [CuttingEEG](#) conference series.

2. When? October 16th - October 19th 2023

3. Where? Everywhere! We have Gardens spread around the world. Get in touch and tell us where you are from so we can help you organize, and synchronize with neighboring Gardens (if any).

4. How? Each Garden runs independently with some support from the global organization. Gardens offer different types of activities (talks, tutorials, etc....), each of which earns the Garden a "Badge" ([badges description here](#)). In order to know which badges you are eligible for, you can fill in [this survey](#)! And once the main features of your Garden are defined, you can sow your garden and declare it to the general organization using this form : [plant your garden](#).

5. How much? It's free! We don't charge anything to join Gardens. We only ask that participants become members of the CuttingEEG association. We're happy to help with planning, but you are responsible for your own budget.

Voilà! We hope you got the idea! Below, you will find general, and more detailed information, guides and various resources to help you organize your own Garden.

If you are interested, don't hesitate to get in touch with us via mail at contact@cuttingeeg.org or via mattermost using [this link](#).

Note that the information below is **color coded** depending on your badges, so that you know what you need for your own local event:

[Attendee]

[Tutorials]

[Posters]

[Speaker] -> already handled by general organization

[Satellite]

General information

[1. Exemple Gardens](#)

[2. Step 1: Main checklist before you start](#)

[3. Step 2: Style your Garden with badges](#)

[4. A Month Ahead \(~September 2023\)](#)

[5. A Week Ahead \(~October 2023\)](#)

[6. On-Site!](#)

[7. Aftermath](#)

1. Example Gardens

1.1 The minimal Garden project

The minimal Garden is very simple. You just need to secure a room with a video projector and internet connection for 2 hours 4 days in a row.

We consider this the main advantage of following the CuttingGardens organization: stepping in is really easy! You get a great "cutting-edge" program for free (note that we ask attendees to become members of CuttingEEG for a fee)! You don't need a lot of energy, but you can just book a room and be part of the CuttingGardens experience.

By offering to broadcast the plenary lectures, your Garden will earn an ["Attendee badge"](#).

Get in touch if this is what you are planning. We'll be happy to set you up for great fun and a lot of MEEG methods!

1.2 The medium sized Garden

If you feel like offering the full experience of the real CuttingGardens event, then you may add a few custom activities to your Garden: Tutorials, Posters, Satellite events...

A medium Garden size could offer two key tutorials with some of the most advanced toolboxes for MEEG analysis. Some tutorials are going to happen live, while others will be pre-recorded. You will be welcome to choose the ones you like and earn your ["Tutorial badge"](#).

Perhaps will you choose: "Introduction to MEEG data analysis with MNE-Python", or perhaps more adventurously "Power-up your EEG analysis with the UNFOLD toolbox" (names are fictive for now, but we're preparing a large catalog of tutorials).

In addition, you know of two postdocs in your institute who have got interesting results in their last EEG experiment. Offering them a stage to showcase these results is easy. One will offer a lecture on his experiment, and the other will broadcast a tutorial with her toolbox so everybody can start using her promising new method! These two sessions will earn you a ["Speaker badge"](#).

On the third evening, you will even take your participants to the local pub for a few drinks. They are going to love it, and your Garden will earn a ["Satellite badge"](#).

1.3 The full experience Garden

Now that you've realized the potential of the CuttingGardens experience, you want it all.

You block the full four days to get maximum latitude for all your dreams. You have a local team of enthusiasts who are going to help you.

Your meeting will start with the plenary lectures of the first day, followed by 5 parallel sessions with 5 toolboxes you've found in the provided list (still in the making!). Your ["tutorial badge"](#) is secured, but you also want your participants to solve their own data analysis problems so you organize a satellite hackathon on the second and third afternoons and earn your ["satellite badge"](#).

Your local institute has expertise in "MEEG with babies", so you have thought of three local speakers who will talk about this on the fourth afternoon. This session may well be advertised via the general CuttingGardens website if you add it to your own event website.

Your event wouldn't feel complete without some real entertainment. You've heard about a local art collective that has learned to trigger visual effects with a new type of BCI. It's all set up, and you will earn your ["satellite badge"](#).

These are just three basic examples to reveal the potential of participating in CuttingGardens as a local Gardener. Keep reading, and be in touch with us (contact@cuttingeeg.org or via [mattermost](#)). [This form](#) could help you create your Garden . We can help!

2. Step 1: Main checklist before you start

2.1 Contact point and effective communication

Choosing the right contact point within the CuttingGardens General Organization Committee is crucial to ensure effective communication and be guided during the organization of your attendance. If you are interested in hosting a Garden, please contact the CuttingGardens General Organization Committee Contact@CuttingEEG.org. You can (and should!) also join our Mattermost channel ([here](#)) for instantaneous communication.

2.2 Securing the venue

Be sure to have access to a proper venue depending on the badge(s) you have. You can ask your institution to provide space for your event, or you can rent a venue for a price (see costs and funding below). Remember to reserve your space well in advance. When choosing a site, try to keep in mind the ease of access with a variety of transportation methods, and that it is accessible for persons with reduced mobility.

2.3 Costs and funding

As you can imagine, having the financial resources to support your Garden is crucial. You can ask your local institution (lab, university...) to sponsor your event and/or apply for a grant. You are responsible for seeking your own funding but the CuttingGardens Organization Committee can help you apply and write applications (get in touch!).

Depending on its badges, your Garden will have different needs and costs. We are providing a [budget template](#) to organize and keep track of your budget, feel free to copy it and adapt it to your needs. We also provide [grant application materials](#) to help you fill in your own grant applications!

In addition, the global organization will help local organizers cover their costs. We are actively seeking financial support that could include travel and accommodation costs for global speakers traveling to local Gardens. At the moment, we cannot guarantee that this will be successful.

A direct financial contribution of local Gardens to the global organization is not demanded, but we request that conference participants become members of [CuttingEEG](#), our home organization for a cost. The amount of this membership will be discussed with individual Gardens organizing committees so as to prevent prohibitively high costs for local gardens. It is customary for CuttingEEG events to offer a few participation fee waivers for participants in need for this kind of help.

2.4 Teamwork

In order to plant your Garden, you will need the help of several “gardeners”! Get in contact with your co-workers and fellow researchers to be part of the Organization Committee. **The more, the merrier!**

When recruiting your local Organization Committee remember to pay special attention to diversity: try to have an equal representation of all genders and allow researchers at all career stages to participate and help (see Code of conduct section below).

2.5 Code of conduct

CuttingEEG has a [Code of Conduct](#) to which you must adhere to for your own Garden.

This code of conduct sets the norms of scientific integrity and open science practices, ensures equality and inclusion, avoids wrongdoing throughout the event, and supports an inviting and inclusive environment accepted by all.

Please make sure that all participants, including speakers, teaching assistants, volunteers, and organizers, read and understand the Code of Conduct ahead of time.

As we all know, excessive alcohol consumption can lead to inappropriate behavior, and we call on the organizers' responsibility to maintain a professional, welcoming environment for all attendees. Offering a variety of non-alcoholic beverages at all social events is mandatory. For more information about the catering options and alcohol use and service, please also read the information under the Food and refreshments section.

3. Step 2: Style your Garden with badges

3.1 Organize the schedule

The CuttingGardens conference offers to broadcast “plenary talks” simultaneously online around the globe. Part of the CuttingGardens experience entails a feeling of global community to which these relatively brief moments of worldwide connection and communication are expected to contribute a lot. All local Gardens are therefore asked to participate in these online plenary talks in synch.

Each garden is then free to build its local schedule with (lots of) special events, but to maximize the feeling of taking part in the same event worldwide, we ask that these local events do not overlap with the plenary talks.

Broadcasting plenary talks earns a Garden the "Attendee" badge.

Save the date template email!

Hello all,

CuttingEEG (<https://cuttingeeg.org/>) is an annual international scientific meeting about **cutting-edge methods for EEG/MEG research on neurophysiology**.

For the first time, the 2023 edition, named **CuttingGarden** (<https://cuttinggardens2023.org/>) will be distributed : events will happen simultaneously in several locations (aka. Gardens) across the world, with a common global program, broadcasted to all locations, and local programs made of talks, tutorials, posters, social events, satellites.. as each Garden (optionally) sees fit.

The **Lyon Neuroscience Research Center** is organizing a Garden and invites you to participate.

Save the date! The event will take place from **October 16th to 19th, 2023 in Lyon**.

To stay informed and/or contribute to the organization of this event, please contact lyon.garden.2023@gmail.com.

“Share knowledge globally, build competence locally”

3.2 Preparing tutorials [Tutorials Gardens Only]

The Organizing Committee provides a [list of tutorials](#) on several topics (e.g., M/EEG, statistics, GitHub, ...). Each tutorial Garden can host one or more tutorials.

There are several types of tutorials:

- **Full-blown hands-on sessions** (appropriate for toolboxes with high visibility in the community) meant to 1) offer a practice session to participants and 2) offer a specific training for local teaching assistants (TAs) with the aim of enabling them to offer such tutorials independently in the future. The TAs are only required to have some practice with the subject of the tutorial (e.g., how to install the software, starting up, and doing basic data analysis). Before the event, TAs will be trained by the main teacher (i.e., toolbox developer) about the specific content of the tutorial. During the event, the main teacher will broadcast the tutorial live for everyone, and TAs will provide local support in each Garden. Hand-on sessions will probably require a dedicated space for the participants to plug and use their own laptop, in addition to a broadcast system and some IT support for the participants. One Tutorial Garden will physically host the main teacher (at the teacher's discretion).
- **Demo tutorials** are shorter sessions with a live demo from the main teacher. Demo tutorials will only require an internet connection, screen and sound system.

In both cases you will need a space equipped with the infrastructure to screen and host the tutorial(s).

3.2 Preparing poster session [Posters Gardens Only]

A poster session needs a dedicated space where people can present and discuss. Depending on its size, you will decide the number of posters allowed. Remember to book this space for the whole duration of the poster session.

A thorough description of the 3-poster-types system proposed by CuttingEEG can be found [here](#) or in the [badges description](#) document.

You can use a submission system with forms to collect posters. Depending on the number of answers you will receive, a selection may be necessary. Do to that, you can use the two template forms proposed in this [folder](#) ('Poster Submission template' and 'Submission review template'). In the past, Please, copy-paste those templates to use it specifically for your garden. You will then have to anticipate the way posters will be attached (you can use for example boards, pins,...), schedule the poster session regarding your general planning and ask participants to bring their poster to the event and put it down at the end.

3.3 Speaker invitations

- Plenary speakers **[Speaker Gardens Only]**

The Global Organization Committee decides and organizes the speakers for the Plenary Talks. We will coordinate with you if a speaker is expected to travel to your Garden.

- Local speakers **[Satellite Gardens Only]**

If you wish to invite one or more speakers to your own local Garden, you are responsible to get in contact and invite the speaker, to organize and financially cover their travel and accommodation costs. If you plan to stream your local speaker's talk, make sure they sign this [consent form](#) for video recording and streaming of their image.

3.4 Website

You can find the CuttingGardens Global website [here](#). In the homepage, you can find an interactive world map showing all the local Gardens and the plenary schedule. Gardens are expected to have their own website. You should take care of creating the webpage of your Garden containing all the necessary information to register and provide your local schedule. Local websites will be linked on a specific page of the global website.

3.5 Registration

You should provide a registration form on your local Garden website. Depending on your costs and funding, you can either make your event free or paid. It is important to keep in mind that a free event is more accessible, but also that registered participants to a free event often don't show up. A minimal cost may therefore be recommended. A registration fee can always be waived upon request. This is the policy that CuttingEEG is usually applying by adding a "fee waiver application" section to the main registration form. Registrants are required to motivate their demand. These applications can be reviewed easily and granted or not, depending on the budgetary constraints before the event.

3.7 Publicizing the event

You should take care of advertising your own local Garden, although the CuttingGardens and CuttingEEG official Twitter accounts will advertise all the local Gardens.

We suggest you open a Twitter account for your own local Garden, and use the mailing-list of your local research centers, Universities or industries.

3.8 Satellite events [\[Satellite Gardens Only\]](#)

There are countless ways of making a scientific event more interesting, attractive, entertaining, productive, and exciting! CuttingEEG has previously hosted art performances, speakers' dinners, parties, "meet the start-ups" sessions, but we could have tried hackathons, escape games, code sprints, city tours, picnics, karaoke nights, citizen science EEG experiments, pop quiz nights... All that matters is that the events and all participants abide by the [Code of conduct](#) of CuttingEEG for scientific, social, and ecological good practices.

Although 3-4 days of meetings fill up very quickly when you're an organizer, these activities bring an important and well deserved break, and make the event more memorable.

3.9 Checklist

It can be useful to create a task list for your event, with individual tasks attributed to specific people. Doing so will help you keep track of what needs to happen when, and avoid overload.

[Here](#) you can find a template checklist created by the CuttingGardens Organization Committee which includes the main topics listed in this guideline. Please copy and modify the tasks according to your own demands and time schedule.

4. A Month Ahead (~September 2023)

4.1 Giveaways

Depending on your budget, funding resources, and ecological consciousness (see [code of conduct](#)), it might be a nice gesture to give away some "goodies" during the event. We emphasize that although these are generally appreciated when they offer a special memory (e.g. with a logo of the event), the amount of wastes and energy consumption that these entail has to be considered. However, those require a dedicated team, good research, and resources to allocate in a timely manner. Therefore plan such arrangements with good time management.

An attractive solution we are currently considering is to offer printed seed paper that could be used to plant [CuttingGardens seeds around the world after the event!](#)

4.2 Speaker and/or TAs reminder [\[Speaker Garden\]](#) [\[Satellite Garden\]](#) [\[Tutorials Garden\]](#)

Do not forget the speakers and or TAs you agreed have many other workloads and duties filling their schedule. Kindly remind them of the updates about the event, their presentation, and the

schedule of the event. If you are inviting speakers from abroad or other cities, make sure to facilitate their accommodation arrangements ahead of time.

4.3 Finalize the program early

Finalizing and publishing a program is a good way to commit organizers (you!) to stick with their plan from the very early stage. It also helps getting attention to your event.

The program template offered by the CuttingGardens provides a basic time-schedule. It is recommended to use this template as a starting point and to adjust it based on your specific needs.

One important tip here: don't forget the breaks! As an event organizer, it is always tempting to fit in more activities than is reasonable. Your participants (and you!) need breaks every hour or so. People are making good use of that time, don't worry!

Also "Panel discussions" are often appreciated. This is why we organize every plenary session in a 3-talks + panel discussion pattern.

4.4 Tutorial checks [Tutorials Gardens Only]

If you plan to run a tutorial track, it is a good idea to poll your participants for their knowledge and experience. The registration time is a good time to do this ("How much experience do you have with this toolbox ?" - beginner - intermediate - expert). It is good practice to adapt the level of the tutorials to the expected participants' level.

It is also good practice to ask tutors to provide the materials ahead of time. And distribute it to participants, especially if loading a dataset is required, as it may overload the local network if all participants start downloading a large dataset during the tutorial.

Power plugs: Bear in mind that during a tutorial session, each participant may need to plug in their laptop computer, so a sufficient number of power outlets should be on site on time. See also [Infrastructure checks](#) below.

4.5 Emergency Backup Plans

It is always recommended to have an emergency plan to react efficiently in the event of any cancellations of an already agreed plan in the program or other higher risking emergencies that might cause health and safety hazards to the attendees (e.g. life-threatening health condition of an attendee, first aid requiring incidents, fire etc.). Please do not forget that emergency situations can develop very quickly, therefore it is always recommended to prepare backup plans to deal with the most common emergency situations.

Considering the possible safety emergency situations, finding a venue that provides all the supplies to take the necessary actions in the existence of an emergency situation should be one

of the priorities. Based on the provided sources, it is always good to have emergency procedures established and made ready to be followed by the event holders. It is recommended to have a team of appointed and trained volunteers to lead the emergency back up plans. The emergency back plans should include basic requirements such as:

- Contact the emergency services immediately.
- Keeping people away from danger.
- Evacuating the area of hazard giving special care and priority to the people with special needs.
- Providing first aid and necessary medical assistance to the persons with injury.
- Liaise with the emergency services.
- Having necessary sign posts to help with emergency situations.

Before the event, make sure that the volunteering team practiced on the location of the exits, contact numbers of the security, and emergency services, fire assembly points, first aid, how to raise an alarm, helping with evacuating the attendees and well-maintained risk management.

Although it might be the case that the occurrence of those events is low in your venue, it is always better to know the environment well and be prepared.

4.6 Infrastructure Checks

It is always recommended to check the venue supplies several times before the event to avoid the last-minute crisis. The basic checks are:

- Network capacity
- Power and plugs
- Video projector
- Microphone
- Board
- Windows
- Heater/Air-conditioning
- Lightning
- Bathrooms
- Ease of access
- Tables
- Chairs
- Room for refreshments
- Bins
- Fire exits and fire extinguishers

4.7 Broadcasting [\[Attendee Garden\]](#) [\[Speaker Garden\]](#) [\[Satellite Garden\]](#)

Recording and/or live broadcasting the talks is generally a good idea that reinforces the global nature of the event. It may be a means to reach a broader audience that was not able to attend

the event in person. The recorded materials will surely be also a useful resource for the community.

Professional technical support is recommended, especially if you consider offering on-site participants the ability to ask questions to a remote speaker. Larsens and other sound loops can completely paralyze a broadcast session and negatively impact the experience of all connected and on-site participants.

In order to broadcast your event, you will need to:

- Secure a camera, including a tripod, and choose an appropriate location in the room.
- Allow your website to broadcast live.
- Allow your website to display the slides (if any) and the speaker as they talk.
- Attendees (both guest speakers and participants) should give their [consent](#) to be recorded. You will need to make sure that they agree (e.g. upon registration).

4.8 Participants' List

Make sure to send an email to all selected candidate participants with all the necessary information as how the event will be run (e.g. event schedule, location, accommodation, bringing their own laptops, including converters and adapters, downloading the data, the [Code of Conduct](#), etc.), underlining the main aim of the event, i.e. sharing knowledge and building competence!

Make sure to also inform any person that could not register due to capacity (if any) so they don't miss the chance to apply to another event.

4.9 Food and refreshments

Hard-working brains require good energy sources and you need to provide well thought and designed food and refreshments throughout your event. As much as your budget allows you, try to go with a variety of options. If you could arrange, a light breakfast is always a good chance for networking while the attendees plan their work for that particular day. Coffee, tea, water, should be provided either throughout the day or within the break times.

Keeping the food healthy and rich should be your main aim for your food choices. Collecting food preferences during registration would help you to plan the food options. It is always good to have vegetarian/vegan/allergy-free/dairy-free options included in your food choices. You might consider foods that would give energy rather than make the attendees sleepy (e.g. heavy on carbs or alcohol, etc.). Please be moderate on providing alcohol including drinks and foods, considering the impact of serving too much alcohol in an event site. Also, please consider the attendees who do not consume alcohol, and provide alternative drinking options displaying both alternatives in the same place to be inclusive.

There might be cases where you might not provide food to the attendees due to the lack of funding. In such cases, please let your attendees know before the event starts and make sure that they either supply their own food or guide them to the local shops and restaurants.

5. A Week Ahead (~October 2023)

5.1 Program

Make sure the event program is finalized together with enough time allocated for set-up, movements and breaks.

5.2 Reminders

Send an email reminder to attendees, sponsors, volunteers, and organizers with the time-schedule and all necessary information (location and contact points).

Make sure that the attendees, speakers, volunteers, suppliers were all provided with the link to the [Code of Conduct](#), and that it has been read before the event participation.

Remind attendees not to forget their own laptops and electrical converters, etc.

5.3 Volunteering checks

Confirm with all volunteers regarding they're signed up duties and who to report back to. They should know their duties and fluidity between the roles in the case of a need for personnel in a situation. They should all know the rules listed in the [Code of Conduct](#), how to act in the case of a crisis and who to direct the people affected by an incident. Similarly, they should be clear about how to act in the case of an emergency situation, being the liaison with the first aiders, security of the building and the organization leaders. If you could create a Gantt chart from the very early stage of job dissemination you can also refer your volunteers to follow it and fill the checkboxes regarding the works that have already been done and completed. While this would help you to be organized as the event host, you can also follow the track of the work that needs to be completed and make additional assignments in case a job needs more volunteers to work on to finish in time.

5.4 Vendor checks

Confirm all time, quantity and service information with the vendors.

5.5 Speakers and TAs checks [\[Speaker Garden\]](#) [\[Satellite Garden\]](#) [\[Tutorials Garden\]](#)

Make sure the [Code of Conduct](#) has been read and agreed upon. Make sure they join the [Mattermost channel](#) and ask them to join and introduce themselves there.

Share the program with them.

Request speakers to send their presentations so that they are published on the website.

5.6 Attendee checks

Make sure the [Code of Conduct](#) has been read and agreed upon. Make sure they join the [Mattermost channel](#) and propose to them to introduce themselves there.

Share the program with them. Remind attendees of the structure of the starting pitches, and ending demos according to the scheduled time plan.

5.6 Tutorial checks [Tutorials Garden]

Share the necessary information regarding the tools, data, slides to download ahead of the event, tutorials to read through, the rooms and the schedule dedicated to the tutorial track.

You can propose a [Mattermost channel](#) to discuss installation issues or general questions relative to a given tutorial.

6. On-Site!

6.1 A day before

Prepare the name badges.

Organize the chairs and desks ready for the sitting plan.

Check projector and microphone, recorder devices, wireless network connection, electrical plugs and extensions, heaters/coolers, lightings.

Layout the notepads, stickers, pens, markers, putty, etc. on the desks.

Layout the cabling through the desks.

Put signs for the route to the event rooms.

Put signs for the route to the restroom and other areas.

Post signs for the emergency info.

Arrange the leaflets with the information about the venue/city.

Arrange to recycle bins if necessary.

Get the prints prepared (name badges, wireless network name/password information sheets, event program, the map of the venue, etc.).

Prepare parking permits.

6.2 The first day

Attendees

Help attendees with the event room and name badges.

Give out promotional materials.

Round up people to attend the presentation.

Speakers and TAs [[Speaker Garden](#)] [[Satellite Garden](#)] [[Tutorials Garden](#)]

Welcome the speakers and TAs.

Check if there is any change with their presentation (mainly does), get the final version anyways.

Confirm the talk time-schedule again.

Provide necessary supplements (USB, electrical plugs, marker, water etc.).

Starting the Event

Welcome address.

Introduce the organizers.

Thank the venue and sponsors.

Explain the history and purpose of the event.

Make the announcements (hashtag, website, time-schedule fire escapes, fire assembly, first aids, make the volunteering helpers known by the attendees).

Explain the logistical issues (meal, the use of the rooms, use of recycling bins, etc.).

Make sure the [Code of Conduct](#) has been read by all the attendees and agreed upon. Give some explanations about why it is important, what to be careful about and what to avoid during the event.

Introduce the Code of Conduct Execution Team in the case of a need for consulting.

Encourage attendees the fair use of the sources.

Encourage attendees to share their contributions to the event.

Encourage attendees to own the event and make it as memorable, productive and fun to be in.

Encourage attendees to introduce themselves to the people around them and to make their badges used to be recognized.

Remind attendees how to proceed/program/end day evaluation-demo-presentations.

6.3 During the event

Coordinate the meal (e.g. lunch, snacks, refreshments, etc.).

Lead people to meal preferences.

Keep close contact with the attendees.

Check on hackers' technical and supplementary requests.

Encourage the use of open science tools.

Facilitate the contact of the attendees to the senior researchers.

Facilitate the access of the attendees to the online sources.

Help attendees with the setups.

Make sure the fair use of social media for the event.

Make sure the video recording and online streaming is working well.

Make sure the [Mattermost channel](#) is used well.

Make sure nothing that would violate the code-of-conduct is allowed.

Publishable materials (photos, recordings, pitch ideas, websites, etc.) are collected and shared through social accounts.

Clean the spaces for the next day.

6.4 The last day

Closure

Farewell talk by the organizers to the attendees.

Acknowledge the volunteers, helpers, attendees, speakers, and sponsors or their contribution.

Encourage the attendance and event organization for the next years.

Encourage the follow-ups on the projects and publications from those projects.

If there is an event afterward, lead people to that event.

Venue Clear ups

Remove the signs.

Collect the garbage.

Collect the cable layouts.

Collect the remaining supplies.

Check for lost items.

7. Aftermath

7.1 Evaluation and learning

Sponsors

Send a thank you to all the sponsors with event highlights and photos as evidence of the event's success.

Send a post-event survey to all the sponsors to collect information in order to improve next years' Cutting EEG event(s).

Attendees

Send a certificate of attendance to all the attendees.

Send a post-event survey to all the attendees to collect information in order to improve next years' Cutting EEG event(s).

Volunteers

Acknowledge all the volunteers and event organizers on the appropriate platform(s) for their contribution.

Organizers

List all the negative and positive event experiences in an internal file to make sure they are known and to make sure that the negatives are not repeated next time.

Compute how much the event cost, both in total and per person, for next years' cost calculations.

Let know those information to the Global Organization Committee, and give your feedback !

Write a blog post with some general observations about the event, along with some highlights and success photos. Collect these photos and include some of them in next year's Cutting EEG/Garden website.